

RF Transmissivity Measurements of a Multilayered Circular Transparency to Characterize Attenuation Behavior Over a Frequency Range from 500 MHz to 18 GHz

Roderick L. Robinson

Avionic Systems Division
Systems Engineering Branch
NASA Johnson Space Center
2101 NASA Road 1
Houston, Texas USA

Robert C. Scully

Avionic Systems Division
Systems Engineering Branch
NASA Johnson Space Center
2101 NASA Road 1
Houston, Texas USA

Abstract

Astronauts engaged in preparatory activities prior to Extravehicular Activity (EVA) may spend one or more hours inside the middeck airlock that has been partially evacuated to the vacuum of space. During this time, the astronauts may wish to review and update non-critical mission information and EVA particulars via a Radio Frequency Local Area Network (RF LAN) connection implemented on a laptop computer. In order to accomplish this, the RF transmission must pass through a multilayer 4-inch transparency, and then propagate to a downlink node located inside the Space Shuttle Orbiter (SSO) vehicle. This paper describes the processes used to verify the transmissivity (essentially the inverse of shielding effectiveness) of such a transparency. Two methods of measurement were employed. The results of each were correlated together after the fact, and showed good agreement.

INTRODUCTION

An older, MIL-STD-461A compatible electromagnetic interference (EMI) measurement chamber, lacking any RF absorber, was used for the first part of this test. This chamber was selected because it was felt this more closely resembled, in an electromagnetic sense, the environment of the middeck airlock ultimately destined for the application. An instrumentation access panel was removed from one end of the chamber, and transmitting and receiving antennas were located on either side of the opening. A frequency sweep from 500 MHz to 18 GHz was then performed to establish a baseline. Following this, the transparency was mounted in the opening, and the frequency sweep was again performed. After this measurement was completed, a more traditional shielding effectiveness measurement was performed on a table top in the lab. The data from each of these tests was found to exhibit good agreement, thus lending confidence in the values obtained. Finally, a test was performed to characterize the possible attenuation of the signal after passing through the transparency, with a small receiving antenna located at various positions within the chamber itself. The transmitter was placed outside the chamber, and a measurement of signal strength was made with the receiver at 10 different locations. In almost all cases with

the receiver held between 3 and 4 feet off the ground, the signal strength was found to be greater than or equal to 90% of the unobstructed value.

BACKGROUND

Astronauts engaged in preparatory activities prior to EVA often spend one or more hours inside the middeck airlock that has been partially evacuated to the vacuum of space. An external view of the middeck airlock is shown below in Figure 1.

Figure 1. External View of the SSO Vehicle
Middeck Airlock

Airlock Description

The SSO vehicle middeck airlock accommodates astronaut EVA operations. The airlock permits EVA crewmembers to transfer from the middeck crew compartment into the payload bay in EVA Mobility Units (EMUs), without the need to depressurize the orbiter crew cabin. The internal airlock provides launch and entry stowage of up to four EMUs, while the external airlock can stow two EMUs. Both types of airlock contain the interfaces and associated displays and controls for the orbiter systems that support EMU operation and servicing. Sized to accommodate a two-person EVA, the internal airlock dimensions have a

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diameter of 63 inches, a length of 83 inches, and two D-shaped 40-inch-diameter openings (three for external airlock). The internal airlock's volume measures 150 cubic feet, while the external airlock has a volume of 185 cubic feet. Support functions performed in the airlock include depressurization and repressurization, EVA equipment recharge, and EVA equipment checkout, donning, and communications. All EVA gear, checkout panel, and recharge stations are located against the internal walls of the airlock.

Airlock Hatches

Two pressure-sealing hatches are mounted on the internal airlock, while the external airlock contains three of these hatches. The inner hatch is located on the exterior of the airlock opening into the middeck. The inner hatch isolates the airlock from the crew cabin. The outer hatch isolates the airlock from the unpressurized payload bay when closed and permits the EVA crewmembers to exit from the airlock to the payload bay when open. The external airlock's third hatch is an additional upper, outer hatch that will be used for docking operations. Each hatch has six interconnected latches with gearbox and actuator, a window, a hinge mechanism with hold-open device, a differential pressure gauge on each side, and two equalization valves.

Airlock repressurization is controlled from the middeck or inside the airlock. It is performed by equalizing the airlock and cabin pressure with airlock-hatch-mounted equalization valves on the inner hatch. Depressurization of the airlock is controlled from inside the airlock. The airlock is depressurized by venting the airlock pressure overboard. The two D-shaped airlock hatches are installed to open toward the primary pressure source, the orbiter crew cabin, to achieve pressure-assist sealing when closed. Each hatch opening is 40 inches in diameter, yet with one side being flat, the minimum dimension is 36 inches.

The 4-inch-diameter window in each airlock hatch is used for crew observation from the cabin to the airlock and the airlock to the payload bay. The dual window panes are made of polycarbonate plastic and are mounted directly to the hatch using bolts fastened through the panes. Each airlock hatch has dual pressure seals to maintain the airlock's pressure integrity. One seal is mounted on the airlock hatch and the other on the airlock structure. A leak check quick disconnect is installed between the hatch and the airlock pressure seals to verify hatch pressure integrity before flight.

Each airlock hatch has the following design characteristics: (1) capable of being fully locked/unlocked from either side, (2) designed for 2000 open/close cycles, (3) one-handed operation by astronaut in pressure suit, (4) capable of opening against 0.2 psid maximum, (5) latches capable of

withstanding 20 g's in the +X direction, and (6) actuator handle load of 30 pounds maximum.

The gearbox with latch mechanisms on each hatch allows the flight crew to open or close the hatch during transfers and EVA operations. The gearbox and the latches are mounted on the low-pressure side of each hatch, with a gearbox handle installed on both sides to permit operation from either side of the hatch. Three of the six latches on each hatch are double-acting with cam surfaces that force the sealing surfaces apart when the latches are opened, thereby acting as crew-assist devices. To latch or unlatch the hatch, the gearbox handle must be rotated 440°.

The hatch actuator/gearbox is used to provide the mechanical advantage to open and close the latches. The hatch actuator lock lever requires a force of 8 to 10 pounds through an angle of 180° to unlatch the actuator. A minimum rotation of 440° with a maximum force of 30 pounds applied to the actuator handle is required to operate the latches to their fully unlatched positions.

The hinge mechanism for each hatch permits a minimum opening sweep into the airlock or the crew cabin middeck.

The inner hatch of the internal airlock (airlock to crew cabin) is pulled or pushed forward to the crew cabin approximately 6 inches. The hatch pivots up and to the right side. Positive locks are provided to hold the hatch in both an intermediate and a full-open position. The outer hatch of the internal airlock (airlock to payload bay) opens and closes to the contour of the airlock wall. The hatch is hinged to be pulled first into the airlock and then forward at the bottom and rotated down until it rests with the low-pressure (outer) side facing the airlock ceiling (middeck floor). The hatch has a holdopen hook that snaps into place over a flange when the hatch is fully open. To support and protect the hatch against the airlock ceiling, the hatch incorporates two deployable struts.

The configuration of the external airlock, planned for International Space Station (ISS) operations, contains an inner hatch, an EV hatch, and a docking hatch. The inner hatch of the external airlock (airlock to crew cabin middeck) has the same opening mechanism as the outer hatch of the internal airlock. The hatch is hinged so that it can be pulled into the middeck and rotated down until it rests on the middeck floor. The EV hatch of the external airlock (airlock to payload bay) also opens in the same manner. The docking hatch, located on the floor of the external airlock (toward the payload bay doors), is hinged to be pulled into the airlock and then rotated until the low pressure side rests against the airlock wall facing toward the nose of the orbiter. The external airlock hatches also have hold-open protection and deployable struts for support against the airlock structure.

Test Purpose and Preparation

During EVA preparation time inside the middeck airlock, the astronauts frequently review non-critical mission information and EVA particulars. On occasion, they may also wish to update this information. Most desirable is the ability to do so via an RF LAN connection implemented on a laptop computer. In order to accomplish this, the RF transmission must pass through the multilayer 4-inch diameter window in the airlock, and then propagate to a downlink node located inside the SSO vehicle.

In test planning discussions, it was felt that the test should replicate the actual physical geometry as closely as possible. NASA Johnson Space Center (JSC) has full-scale mock-ups of the SSO vehicle and its various cabin sections, and this was the first choice for the test set-up. However, the mock-up of the middeck airlock turned out to be constructed of wood, and was in no way sealed to RF penetration.

Fortunately, the Space Shuttle Program (SSP) EMI measurement chamber was available at the time. This chamber was originally built to accommodate small to medium sized equipment intended for utilization by the SSP. At the time this chamber was constructed, MIL-STD-461A was the driving EMI requirements source, so the chamber design did not include any provisions for inclusion of RF absorber materials.

This chamber has a central room used for equipment measurements, with two ancillary rooms on either side, and is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. JSC Space Shuttle EMI Measurement Chamber

Now, the chamber central room has dimensions of 15' X 10' X 8', giving a volume of 1200 cubic feet, which is about 8 times larger than the middeck internal airlock volume. Even so, it was felt that using the chamber would provide an acceptable simulation, for several reasons of which the following two were considered most persuasive:

- Resonance effects were expected to be similar because of reflections and discontinuities in both the airlock and the chamber caused by tables, equipment randomly located in the room, et cetera.
- Expected regions of highest attenuation in the airlock were close to the window, against the wall. These regions could easily be examined in the measurement chamber.

Having made the decision to use the measurement chamber, the next challenge was to acquire and mount the 4-inch diameter transparency in such a fashion as to allow for a measurement procedure to be executed.

The transparency, as described previously, is actually two polycarbonate panes of plastic that are held in place inside the hatch door by a circular spreader ring, two pressure seals, and four bolts that pass through the panes themselves. The panes and seals were available for the test, but not the hatch or the circular spreader ring. So, a compression fixture, fabricated from wood covered with aluminum foil, was designed to rigidly clamp the provided panes and seals, using four 6-inch long 1/4 X 20 screws and appropriate hardware. Two pictures of the resulting fixture are shown in Figures 3 and 4 below.

Figure 3. Transparency Fixture, Test Room Side

Figure 4. Transparency Fixture, Support Room Side

The fixture was designed to fit into the 12" X 12" opening vacated by the interface panel communicating between the test room and the support room of the Shuttle EMI

measurement chamber (see Figure 2, left hand side). As can be seen in Figures 3 and 4, the completed fixture did this very well. The aluminum tape around the periphery of the fixture allowed for a good RF tight seal on the test room side, assuring that any signal that was sensed in the support room would result from having passed through the transparency, and not leaked around the edges of the fixture.

Chamber Test Execution

Once the transparency fixture was assembled and checked for fit into the chamber wall (the aluminum tape was not applied until later in the measurement process), it was removed and the measurement process was begun. The desired frequency range for the test was from 200 MHz to 18 GHz. Because of equipment availability, the upper range was checked first. Two ETS ridged waveguide horns, model number 3115, were mounted on tripods and placed at an equal distance to either side of the test room/support room wall, as shown in Figures 5 and 6.

Figure 5. Placement of 3115 Horn, Test Room Side

After collecting baseline data from 2 GHz to 18 GHz (i.e., no window), the fixture was replaced in the interface opening, and the frequency sweep was repeated. Additional data was taken from 1 GHz to 2 GHz, first with the window fixture in place, and then with the fixture removed, using the same two horns. The data for both frequency ranges is shown in Figures 7 and 8 (baseline is in red; attenuated signature in black).

After completing these two frequency range sweeps, the horns were changed out for two ETS ridged waveguide horns, model number 3106. These horns were placed in similar fashion to the two model 3115 horns, as shown in Figures 9 and 10, and data was then taken from 200 MHz to 1 GHz for both the open interface panel, and the window fixture in place. The data for this frequency range is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 6. Placement of 3115 Horn, Support Room Side

Figure 7. Baseline/Attenuation Data - 2 GHz to 18 GHz

Figure 8. Baseline/Attenuation Data - 1 GHz to 2 GHz

Figure 9. Placement of 3106 Horn, Test Room Side

Figure 10. Placement of 3106 Horn, Support Room Side

Figure 11. Baseline/Attenuation Data - 0.2 GHz to 1 GHz

Examination of these data plots indicates a maximum attenuation for the window near 440 MHz of approximately 28 dB. Near the RF LAN operating frequency of 2.4 GHz, the attenuation is more nearly 15 dB. Average attenuation across the entire frequency range appears to be on the order of 10 dB.

Traditional Test Execution

As a means of independent check against this data, it was determined to remove the window fixture and using a more traditional method, measure the insertion loss of the window assembly on the bench. Two horn adapters were placed together, and a baseline sweep was performed from 0.5 GHz to 18 GHz. Then, the window assembly was placed between the two horn adapters, and the measurement was repeated. The data from these two sweeps is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Traditional Baseline/Attenuation Data
0.5 GHz to 18 GHz

This data shows a delta similar to that observed in the chamber test near the 2.4 GHz RF LAN operating frequency of approximately 12 dB. Note at approximately 3.4 to 3.6 GHz, in both the data sets, a fairly large attenuation is noticeable in the data. Again, near 9.25 GHz, the data separates in both sets to an average of approximately 10 to 12 dB, with the exception of the spike anomaly in the chamber data. Finally, similar to the first data set, the average attenuation across the entire frequency range seen in the more traditional data set appears to be on the order of 10 dB.

Empirical Percent Signal Strength Test

Having the data above provided much better confidence in the performance of the RF LAN link through the 4-inch transparency in the airlock. However, nothing is quite as

good as a demonstration test of the actual components that need to be able to communicate. So, an empirical test was devised to determine the simulated performance of the link between an RF LAN equipped laptop computer and the receiving downlink node.

In order to perform the test, the laptop was loaded with a test software routine that reported the received signal in terms of percentage, based on a threshold power associated with an acceptable Bit Error Rate (BER) for effective data transfer. Ten locations, labeled A through J, were marked off inside the test chamber, as indicated in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Laptop Test Locations Inside The Test Room.

The receiving unit was placed in the support room, and then the laptop was placed at each of the 10 test room locations, first on the floor, and then at a distance of 3 and 4 feet above the floor. The data is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Percent Received Signal Strength.

Location	Signal Strength, Floor Level	Signal Strength, Above Floor
A	90	90
B	< 70	90
C	< 70	90
D	< 70	85
E	70	90
F	90	90
G	90	90
H	90	90
I	80	90
J	80	90

CONCLUSION

This paper has described the processes used to verify the transmissivity (essentially the inverse of shielding effectiveness) of a 4-inch transparency existing in the middeck airlock through which it is necessary to be able to pass an RF LAN signal from a laptop computer to a remotely located downlink node inside the SSO vehicle. Two methods of measurement were employed. The results of each were correlated together after the fact, and showed good agreement. A final, empirical test was performed that demonstrated a high percentage of signal strength could be expected to appear at the downlink node, irrespective of the laptop's location within the middeck airlock.